

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF FAMILY RELATIONS

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ANNOTATION. This article highlights the relationship between children and parents, relationship between parents, factors in family relationships, dynamics, pedagogical etiquette in dealing with children to ensure a positive parent-child relationship.

KEY WORDS: parent, child, attitude, education, morality, sincerity, kindness, love, tradition.

In recent years, scientific research on family and intergenerational relations has been gaining momentum all over the world. Among them, foreign psychologists and sociologists, A. Willy, E. Durkheim, P. Jane in France, T. Schreiber in Germany, K. Buhler, V. Matthews, DJ Bruner, S. Hall, W. James, D. Cheney in America, Several works in this field have been carried out by E. Clapared and many other researchers in Switzerland. In our view, child-parent relationships, parenting attitudes, and parenting practices are related, but at the same time complementary and often used synonymously. should be distinguished from each other.

The peculiarity of the relationship between children and parents is that they consist of two-way relations, and both parties actively form the system of parent-child relations. Although these relations are not equal relations from the beginning, they always strive for equal rights. The formation of the child's personality is considered a product of such relationships. Thus, the relationship between children and parents can be interpreted as a system of relationships between adults and children who are directly related: they appear with the birth of a child, and the interaction of parents and children in the process of cooperation, it acquires an essence characterized by its own dynamics and uniqueness. Such relations have the following three factors: the cultural and historical content of parent-child relations. It is very important to have the right relationship with children in the family. The family has great opportunities to raise children in the spirit of love for the Motherland, conscious attitude to work and national wealth, tolerance for defects. The family, in particular, has great opportunities in educating the feelings and emotional culture of the child. In order for the relationship between parents and children to become positive, parents should observe pedagogical etiquette when interacting with their children. The fact that every word spoken by the parents has an effect, the form of the word is spoken, and the face is open or expressive in accordance with the form of the word, increases the effectiveness of the pedagogical effect. On the

contrary, non-observance of pedagogic manners, excessive love for a child, or cruel and harsh treatment causes a violation of the interaction between parents and children. In order to ensure positive relations between parents and children, it is necessary to treat and treat each child separately. The child's age and condition at that time should be taken into account. In order to better understand the child's age and situation, we need to put ourselves in the child's place. Then we can understand the child's inner world and desires. The creation of a positive relationship between parents and children largely depends on the fact that parents know their children, their character, character traits, interests, etc. In this regard, every parent, first of all, should know their children in every way and treat them accordingly.

It is appropriate to make the following conclusions and recommendations based on the above-mentioned points:

- Children of parents who treat children with sincerity, but allow them to do a lot of things, have such characteristics as activity, independence, friendship, creativity, and a wide opportunity for the formation of negative conditions.

- The children of parents who take care of their children sincerely, but limit them in many ways, are polite and submissive, and they show less desire for creativity and independence.

- Children of parents who are cold towards their children, but who allow them to do a lot of things, are often indifferent to their parents, but do not always show it in their behavior. Also, they are usually shy, do not trust adults, prefer social isolation.

- A close relationship between a child and a parent can stimulate the development of self-awareness. In accordance with the previous conclusions, our following recommendations are intended for parents and teachers.

- Parents and students should have a complete idea about the features of the formation of self-awareness in a person.

- Parents should learn to correctly assess their children's interests, possibilities and abilities. Only in this way can they teach their children proper self-evaluation and self-development.

- Taking into account that the disruption of the psychological climate in the family creates negative characteristics in the child's behavior, it is appropriate for parents to get used to creating an atmosphere of cooperation in the family.

- Sincere communication creates the qualities of honesty, generosity, and independence in a child's personality. This allows parents to have regular live communication with their children.
- Self-awareness is one of the factors of acquiring moral standards in a person. In this case, it is very important for parents to act as a "good role model" for their children.

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